

The Impact of Women Leadership on Psychological Capital A Study on Nurses in Egypt

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Abstract

The objective of the research is to examine the Impact of Women Leadership (WL) on Psychological Capital (PsyCap) of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt. The research population consists of all nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt. Due to time and cost constraints, the researcher adopted a sampling method to collect data for the study. The appropriate statistical methods were used to analyze the data and test the hypotheses.

The research has reached a number of results, the most important of which are: (1) the level of leadership characteristics of women was high, because the leader possesses the characteristics of her advantage effectively and influential on the performance of workers, (2) the level of empathy is the highest, due to the physiological nature of women that distinguish them from males. (3) the level of cooperation is high. This is an indication that this characteristic needs to be further developed and strengthened by increasing the level of participation and interaction between the president and the staff to increase the level of effectiveness, (4) there is a statistically significant effect of the characteristics of women leaders in the development of PsyCap, (5) there is a statistically significant impact of the characteristics of women leadership in developing confidence (self-efficacy) due to the nature of women leadership of workers, (6) there is a statistically significant impact of the characteristics of women's leadership in the development of optimism, (7) there is a statistically significant impact of the characteristics of women leadership in the development of hope, (8) there is a statistically significant impact of the characteristics of women leadership in developing resilience, (9) the level of characteristics of women leadership was high and this is due to the organization in a positive way, and (10) the level of PsyCap was somewhat moderate. This is due to the presence of ineffective practices in the right investment of PsyCap.

The study referred to a number of recommendations; the most important of which are (1) increase and strengthen the practices of women leadership characteristics. This is due to the positive impact on subordinates, through increased support to senior management, documenting successful experiences, and capacity development through specialized training programs, (2) the need to pay attention to the PsyCap significantly. This is due to its importance and its impact on the psychology and the work of the individual in the organization and because of the benefits and competitive advantage of the organization, (3) allow women in the fields of recruitment and involve them more in the work to nurture their strength of expertise, (4) the need not to limit women because they are women only and leave this negative culture, because women have high leadership skills that excelled by and elevated the field of work, (5) the need to continue to look for the characteristics of women's leadership, which is due to the availability, but did not write much, and urge to invest in PsyCap. This will be through further studies where there is a clear lack of those studies on the one hand and the urgent need for them on the other, and (6) the necessity and importance of researching the characteristics of women leadership in different sectors.

Keywords: Women Leadership, Psychological Capital

1. Introduction

In today's competitive environment, there are many challenges facing organizations. There is also an urgent need to develop and strengthen the human resources capacities of organizations to meet these challenges. Psychological Capital (PsyCap) is a contemporary theme that has a significant impact on human resource development and productivity (Luthans et al., 2007).

PsyCap needs influences to increase investment in it, and leadership in general of these influences. Some studies revealed that there is an impact of leadership in PsyCap (Murray, 2014).

Women's leadership is a form of administrative leadership that affects PsyCap. It represents a set of characteristics that enable women to determine their own destiny and increase their self-confidence to assume leadership and managerial positions and develop their ability to achieve superior performance (Weidenfeller, 2012).

Women leadership is a new concept that has not been adequately written and researched, and studies are attempting to close that scientific gap to that term (Cook & Glass, 2014).

Because the term Women leadership is modern, the researchers highlighted it to learn more about women's leadership and the areas where women are able to lead more effectively (Kumar, 2013).

There are also studies that indicate that few women hold senior management positions in organizations (Heckman, 2013). This is not because of their lack of competence, skills and experience, but because of the many obstacles and barriers that women face today in organizations (Petru, 2015).

The characteristics of women leadership, especially self-confidence and patience, contribute to the development of social aspects. It is well known that PsyCap is a component of social aspects (Rouleau-Carroll, 2014).

PsyCap has been dealt with in a variety of businesses, but it extends beyond human and social capital "Instead of the philosophy "What do you know?" Or" Who do you know?". PsyCap has been neglected by academics and business practitioners, although it is an important part of human capital (what do I know?) and social capital (whom do I know?) (Luthans et al., 2004).

PsyCap is an individual's positive, scalable mental state characterized by confidence (Intuitiveness) to make the necessary efforts to succeed in challenging tasks, to create positive characteristic (optimism) about success now and in the future, to persevere towards achieving goals and when necessary reorienting paths (Hope) to succeed in achieving goals, and the ability to rebound (resilience) to succeed when exposed to problems and tribulations (Avey, 2014).

2. Literature Review

2.1. Woman Leadership

2.1.1. Woman Leadership Concept

Women's leadership is a rare topic. It is a new term on the scene. It was first mentioned at the Mexico Forum in 1975 and this year is an international women's year (Heckman, 2013).

Leadership in the general sense is the ability to direct and influence subordinates (Rouleau-Carroll, 2014)

Leadership means the ability to guide and encourage change in the group (Pellkey-Landes, 2002). Leadership is more than just a science that is applied, but it is a moral craft.

Leadership encompasses beliefs and dreams along with theories of practice in taking action, as the leader can solve problems and impose his personality and knowledge (Toogood, 2012).

Women Leadership is a set of distinctive characteristics of women's performance compared to men that enable women to achieve desired results and effectiveness and maintain success (Rouleau-Carroll, 2014).

Women Leadership is a hard work that requires the use of many skills and techniques to succeed, and sometimes requires women to use different techniques to gain professional credibility or even to adopt male characteristics (Heckman, 2013).

Women Leadership is a set of characteristics and behaviors that are associated with women such as people development, expectations and rewards, inspiration and decision-making participation, which enable them to perform leadership tasks better than men (Desvaux et al., 2007).

Women Leadership is a set of abilities and characteristics that women have in performing leadership tasks such as motivation, encouragement, and listening ability (Koneck, 2006).

Women Leadership is a leadership style with a set of characteristics that include collaborative work, relationship building, and caring for others (Shermerhorn, 2005).

2.1.2. Woman Leadership Characteristics

There are a number of distinctive characteristics of women leadership that enable women to achieve desired and effective results and maintain success (Rouleau-Carroll, 2014; Fahmy, 2013; Toogood, 2012; Desvaux et al., 2007; Batts, 2000; Bynum, 2000; Hudak Fandrich, 1994). These characteristics are as follows:

2.1.2.1. Empathy

Empathy is the ability of women leaders to communicate with colleagues more effectively. This gives women strength in their leadership because they can act in critical situations (Vasavada, 2012).

This is in addition to making the decision rationally taking into account the circumstances surrounding subordinates. One of the strategies the leader exercises in dealing with subordinates is to speak, listen to them, communicate with them in person and discuss their issues. This strategy also helps the leader in implementing action strategies (McCullough, 2011).

2.1.2.2. Patience

Patience is the ability to endure adversity and certain situations and the possession of nerves and guide thought properly to reach a certain rational solution. Patience was mentioned as dealing with the situation as a whole, that is, the need for a deeper understanding of the circumstances beyond the norm. Familiarity with leadership is more a representation of patience (Rouleau-Carroll, 2014; Fahmy, 2013).

2.1.2.3. Collaboration

Collaboration is the sharing of work with people to achieve the goals of the organization through good listening and consultation among them. This leads to the adoption of decisions in the manner of democratic consultation, and thus raises the morale of employees in the organizations, and increases the loyalty of staff towards the organization. In order to be an effective leader, the art of this requires collaboration and coexistence with employees, as this is the key to leadership in making the right decision (Fahmy, 2013; McCullough, 2012).

2.1.2.4. Intuitiveness

Intuitiveness is the ability of women to understand the work that must be done and the ability of women to understand things without speaking clearly and explicitly, through their instinct (Rouleau-Carroll, 2014). Intuitiveness also means the ability of the leader to be flexible in thinking when facing one of the difficulties, and to achieve a certain goal, that is, sometimes moving from one goal to another to reach the desired goal (McCullough, 2011).

2.1.2.5. Composure

Composure is the tolerance of the difficulties and hardships facing the leader and to reach success and desired goals. Composure is a very important quality in leading women to their sensitivity, because they are important for example in the process of leadership (Rouleau-Carroll, 2014).

2.2. Psychological Capital

2.2.1. Psychological Capital Concept

PsyCap is the generation of information that has the potential to be applied in education, to create an appropriate organization that meets the requirements of the work as well as information on leadership skills to create the necessary change when individuals achieve prosperity and achieve unique potential in the organization (Corner, 2015).

PsyCap is the positive psychic ability of an individual that is built along the lines of hope, trust, resilience, and optimism (Poon, 2013).

PsyCap is a set of personality traits that contribute to an individual's productivity, and represents a set of positive personal resources that enable individuals to achieve productivity and success in various aspects of life (Gohel, 2012)..

PsyCap is a positive psychological state developed for the individual described through (1) the individual's confidence to make the necessary efforts to achieve success in the performance of challenging tasks, (2) individuals make distinctive positive contributions to current and future success, (3) the individual strives to achieve the goals in order to achieve the desired success, and (4) the ability of the individual to endure when facing various problems and obstacles towards the pursuit of goals (Luthans et al., 2007).

2.2.2. Psychological Capital Dimensions

There are four dimensions of PsyCap. They are self-efficacy, optimism, hope, and resilience. These dimensions have proven valid across different cultures (Han et al., 2012). They can be explained as follows:

1. Self-Efficacy: It is the interaction of individuals working in the organization and expressing their opinions freely without fear or doubt (Lima, 2015). Self-efficacy is the confidence of individuals in their ability to mobilize their motivation, their knowledge resources, and take the necessary actions to successfully accomplish their mandated work within the organization under certain environmental conditions (Luthans & Youssef, 2017). It is the perception or belief of an individual that he or she can successfully perform a particular task (Bandura, 2012). Self-efficacy is the ability to be confident and successful, and to transfer those abilities in a stimulating way to achieve the goal (Chen & Lim, 2012). It is the belief in one's own abilities and skills and their success, regardless of their surroundings (Avey et al., 2010). Self-efficacy is an individual's confidence to make the necessary efforts to succeed in challenging tasks (Luthans et al., 2007).

2. Optimism: It reflects a person's view of events successfully or as a failure. A person who is optimistic views events successfully and the reason for this success is due to internal factors (Brockorny, 2015). Optimism is divided into realistic optimism and unrealistic optimism. Realistic optimism is the result of maintaining a positive view of things in the future, focusing on the positive aspects stemming from the individual's experience, leaving the events of the past, focusing more on the present and looking for opportunities in the future to seize them. Unrealistic optimism reflects the existence of some information that one does not want to retain through certain beliefs, and this leads to the failure to achieve the goals to be achieved (Corner, 2015).

Optimism is the degree to which individuals have an outcome of expectations of positive outcomes, so that they believe that good things will happen to them in relation to their work (Schmitt et al., 2013). Optimistic individuals are distinctive that they have positive expectations about the outcomes of specific events, believing in their ability to succeed in several areas, and persistence and continuing to achieve that success, while when they fail they face that failure through many unlimited contributions (Seligman, 2002). An optimist recognizes the ordeal as a temporary setback and that opportunities remain (Luthans, 2005; Youssef & Luthans, 2007). Optimism refers to creating the positive characteristic and expectations of the best for present and future success (Luthans et al., 2007).

3. Hope: It is to possess the willpower and paths necessary to achieve the desired goals. It is also the belief of the individual that he can find alternative paths to the desired goals and become a catalyst for the use of these paths (Luthans & Youssef, 2017). Hope is the need to persevere in achieving goals and redirecting paths to reach high efficiency. This is the basis of the difference between it and the traditional definition of hope, that is, the traditional definition is to wish for something and one might be disappointed if it is not achieved without retrying (Brockorny, 2015). Hope is a formation of successful will associated with a specific plan, which is aimed at the successful completion of some desired tasks or outputs. Hope is to realize the individual's ability to derive pathways that lead to the desired goals, and to motivate the individual through the power and energy of goal-oriented thinking to use these pathways (Avey, 2014). Hope is the ability to find ways and means to reach the goals that a person aspires to have with positive psychic possibilities. If these methods do not work, he thinks in other ways to reach and persist in the goals to be reached (Javidan & Walker, 2013). Hope includes three main directions: strength, path, and purpose. The direction of force is the will to achieve the desired goal, and it serves as a catalyst to reach that goal. The pathway is the alternative to be pursued in the pursuit of the goal, which is determined by the planning of the situation and the prediction of the obstacles in the way of the goal as a proactive measure to achieve the desired goal (Avey, 2014).

Hope refers to persistence and pursuit of goals, and redirecting paths towards those goals where necessary in order to succeed (Luthans et al., 2007).

4. Resilience: It is an important element associated with improving the performance of the organization as a whole, as change generates high tension in the environment of the organization, so leaders need to pay attention to the element of resilience (Corner, 2015), and develop it in a way that achieves satisfaction and job commitment (Murray, 2014). Resilience is the reaction and positive adaptation that an individual shows when experiencing problems and constraints (Masten & Reed, 2002). Resilience is the positive psychic abilities to rebound or returning from obstacles, uncertainty, conflict, failure, and even severe positive changes and progress achieved by an individual, and increased responsibilities upon him (Luthans, 2002). Resilience is a positive response not only to adverse events but also to positive events that can cause adverse reactions on the part of the individual, as well as in the form of pressures on the individual (Norman, 2006).

The organization can achieve resilience by taking advantage of mistakes and considering them as lessons that generate an opportunity for the organization to develop itself and seize those opportunities through learning, growth and development (Bockorny, 2015). Whenever the organization is flexible, its leaders will also be flexible. Resilience can be developed through three main strategies (1) an asset-focused strategy, which means increasing resilience by building individual assets and increasing the likelihood of success. (2) a strategy of focusing on risk means trying to reduce failure by minimizing risk factors, and (3) a strategy of focusing on the process and trying to build effective mechanisms so that workers can deploy their assets (Poon, 2013). Resilience refers to endurance and a return to the appropriate state in the event of an individual's problems and adversity in pursuit of goals (Luthans et al., 2007).

3. Research Model

The proposed comprehensive conceptual model is presented in Figure (1). The diagram below shows that there is one independent variable for the study of WL. There is one dependent variable PsyCap.

Figure (1)

Proposed Comprehensive Conceptual Model

The proposed comprehensive conceptual model is presented in Figure (1). The diagram shows that there is one independent variable of WL. There is one dependent variable of PsyCap. It shows the rational link between the two types of observed variables.

WL is measured in terms of empathy, collaboration, patience, intuitiveness and composure (Desvaux & Devilland, 2007; Rouleau – Carroll, 2014).

PsyCap as measured consists of self-efficacy, optimism, hope, and resilience (Luthans et al., 2007).

4. Research Questions

The literature suggests that there is a lack of studies on women's leadership, and could not give us a clear idea of women's experiences as leaders (Wedenfeller, 2012).

There is a relationship between experience and PsyCap, but there is a scientific gap that researchers are trying to cover through studies (Drasin, 2014; Galuppo et al, 2011).

The leadership of women is characterized by a different style of leadership. It dominates the feminine character and this is what distinguishes them in leadership from men. This is due to a set of characteristics that are unique to the female personality (Sikdar & Mitra, 2012).

There must be certain characteristics that qualify women to lead women. Studies have identified among the leadership characteristics of both sexes self-development, adaptation and courage, and experience (Desvaux & et al., 2007; Rouleau-Carroll, 2014).

The researcher sees the common characteristics of women working as managers in organizations, which enable them to stay in the job and maintain success and effectiveness are communication, spirit of propaganda, empathy, patience, listening, cooperation, intuitiveness, and composure.

There is a study aimed at identifying management levels and leadership style. The tool used in the study to collect data was the demographic survey. The results of this study state that women should be gender-sensitive. Also, there is no relationship between middle management and leadership style, 55.8% of employees in middle management aspire to reach the top management while 42.1% do not aspire to reach the top management as they prefer a balance between life and work (Koneck, 2006).

Another study aimed at identifying why Qatari women are not represented in the Qatari labor market and the challenges they face in the Qatari society, and the social challenges they face in the labor market. The most important results were that Qatari women prefer jobs in the field of education, that career planning in universities affects the decision of Qatari women to enter the labor market. Personal qualifications are the most important factor in employment. Also, the study pointed to the need to place special emphasis on leadership inequality and fair evaluation of success (Khalifeh, 2011).

In addition, another study aimed to identify the reasons for the under-representation of females in senior management in secondary education. The most important results were that (1) creating awareness of a set of essential skills and methods that allow teachers to pursue the basics of secondary education, (2) presenting the necessary information to female teachers pursuing secondary education to be prepared to meet the challenges facing them, (3) encouraging females who are afraid to enter secondary education because of leaving the profession because of negative experiences, and (4) providing objective information for the development of administrative programs that can assist in the design of instructions to support women who wish to become a high school director. Also, the study found characteristics of female leadership are clear communication, sense of humor, empathy, patience, listening, cooperation, nutrition, intuitiveness, and calmness (Rouleau-Carroll, 2014).

Finally, another study aimed to identify the nature of the relationship between leadership and confidence in police agencies. The questionnaire was distributed to a sample of (169) individuals. The results of the study are that the police officers tend to trust and be strong in police organizations. The recommendation of the study is to do more research on the dynamics of leadership and trust. This is because trust is a complex subject.

The researcher found the research problem through two sources. The first source is to be found in previous studies. There is a lack in the number of literature review that dealt with the analysis of the relationship between WL and PsyCap. This called for the researcher to test this relationship in the Egyptian environment.

The second source is the pilot study, which was conducted in an interview with (30) employees at the industrial companies in Egypt to identify the dimensions of WL and PsyCap. The researcher found through the pilot study several indicators notably the blurred important and vital role that could be played by WL in affecting PsyCap at the industrial companies in Egypt. The research questions of this study are as follows:

- Q1: What is the nature and extent of the relationship between WL (Empathy) and PsyCap at the industrial companies at Sadat city in Egypt?
- Q2: What is the extent of the relationship between WL (Collaboration) and PsyCap at the industrial companies at Sadat city in Egypt?
- Q3: What is the nature of the relationship between WL (Patience) and PsyCap at the industrial companies at Sadat city in Egypt?
- Q4: What is the extent of the relationship between WL (Intuitiveness) and PsyCap at the industrial companies at Sadat city in Egypt?
- Q5: What is the nature and extent of the relationship between WL (Composure) and PsyCap at the industrial companies at Sadat city in Egypt?

5. Research Hypotheses

A study aimed to reveal the relationship between the components of the organizational structure and strength in the light of the theory of organizational behavior. It has been concluded that the literature suggests that the informal strength structures are more positive than in virtual structures. This study found the exact opposite, as the strength in virtual structures is more positive. The study presented a set of recommendations, the most important of which is the continuation of research and development in the field of power and research on the dynamics of organizational behavior (Marinaccio, 2007).

There is another study aimed to reveal the experience of women as an organized leader and to shed light on the experience of women when they are leaders. There are many challenges facing women in the field of leadership such as obstacles to the promotion, and the lack of involvement of women in the development of strategies. The results of the study provided more clarity on how women approach jobs, balance their personal lives, women leadership and control, and the issues they faced in their journey to become a leader (Weidenfeller, 2012).

In addition, another study aimed to identify the reasons for the lack of women in senior management (1) the desire to appoint women leaders as executive directors rather than men as executive directors in organizations, (2) a woman leader shall be replaced as an executive director by a man if the performance of the organization does not improve under her leadership of that organization, (3) women's representation on the Board affects the appointment of women leaders as Executive Directors and this affects their term of office (Cook & Glass, 2014).

Also, another study aimed to identify the reasons that lead women's access to leadership positions through the analysis of their leadership experiences through qualitative data. The study revealed three trends of the importance of motherhood in the leadership role (1) participating women noted that the character of motherhood is a method of improving their performance, (2) the participating women tried to take advantage of motherhood skills to be a way to overcome social problems, and (3) participating women used the method of maternity to solve the problem of sex and earn capital by employing maternity skills in the workplace (Lumby & Azaola, 2014).

Finally, another study aimed to detect the interaction of individuals in the organization with each other according to the function (organization position). The data were collected through two groups, the first consisting of a developmental network survey of top executives. The second group consists of a multisource survey of the executive's co-workers. The results of this study revealed that there is a positive relationship between the position of the job leader and the strength of the developmental leadership network (Yip, 2015).

The following hypotheses were developed to decide if there is a significant correlation between WL and PsyCap.

H1: There is no relationship between WL (Empathy) and PsyCap at the industrial companies at Sadat city in Egypt.

H2: WL (Collaboration) has no statistically significant effect on PsyCap at the industrial companies at Sadat city in Egypt.

H3: There is no relationship between WL (Patience) and PsyCap at the industrial companies at Sadat city in Egypt.

H4: There is no relationship between WL (Intuitiveness) and PsyCap at the industrial companies at Sadat city in Egypt.

H5: There is no relationship between WL (Composure) and PsyCap at the industrial companies at Sadat city in Egypt.

6. Research Population and Sample

The population of the study included only nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt. The total population is 3000 nurses. Determination of respondent sample size was calculated using the formula (Daniel, 1999) as follows:

$$n = \frac{N \times (Z)^2 \times P(1-P)}{d^2(N-1) + (Z)^2 \times P(1-P)}$$

So the number of samples obtained by 343 nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt is as presented in Table (1).

Table (1) Distribution of the Sample Size

Teaching Hospitals	Nurses	Percentage	Sample Size
Shebin El Koum	784	24%	343X 24% = 82
Damanhour	445	14%	343X 14% = 48
Benha	489	15%	343X 15% = 51
Ahmed Maher	448	14%	343X 14% = 48
Galaa	412	13%	343X 13% = 45
Al Mataria	309	9 %	343X 9 % = 31
Al Sahel	358	11%	343X 11% = 38
Total	3245	100%	343X 100% = 343

The annual Statistics for the Information Center of the Public Agency for Teaching Hospitals, 2018

Descriptive statistics are used to describe some of the features of the respondents at the pharmaceutical industry in Egypt who participated in the survey.

Table (2) provides more detailed information about the sample and the measures.

Table (2) Characteristics of Items of the Sample

Variables		Frequency	Percentage
1- Sex	Male	130	43%
	Female	170	57%
	Total	300	100%
2- Marital Status	Single	110	37%
	Married	190	63%
	Total	300	100%
3- Age	Under 30	100	33%
	From 30 to 45	150	50%
	Above 45	50	17%
	Total	300	100%
4- Educational Level	Secondary school	140	47%
	University	160	53%
	Total	300	100%
5- Period of Experience	Less than 5 years	50	17%
	From 5 to 10	210	70%
	More than 10	40	13%
	Total	300	100%

7. Data Collection

The researcher has used the questionnaire for collecting data. The questionnaire is interested in WL and PsyCap of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt. The survey included three questions. The first is related to WL, the second detects PsyCap, the third relates to the demographic variables of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt. About 343 questionnaires were distributed. 300 usable questionnaires. The response rate was 88%. The research depends on the Likert scale for each statement ranging from (5) “full agreement,” (4) for “agree,” (3) for “neutral,” (2) for “disagree,” and (1) for “full disagreement.”

8. Research Variables and Methods of Measuring

The 20-item scale WL section is based on Desvaux & Devilland, 2007 Rouleau– Carroll, 2014. There were four items measuring empathy, four items measuring collaboration, four items patience, four items measuring intuitiveness, and four items measuring composure. The survey form is used as the main tool for data collection in measuring WL of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt.

Also, the 24-item scale PsyCap section is based on Luthans, 2006. There were six items measuring hope, six items measuring optimism, six items measuring resilience, and six items measuring self-efficacy.

Responses to all items scales were anchored on a five (5) point Likert scale for each statement which ranges from (5) “full agreement,” (4) for “agree,” (3) for “neutral,” (2) for “disagree,” and (1) for “full disagreement”.

9. Data Analysis and Hypotheses Testing

The researcher has employed the following methods: (1) Cronbach’s Alpha, (2) Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA), and (3) the statistical testing of hypotheses which includes F- test and T-test. They are found in SPSS.

9.1. Coding of Variables

The main variables, sub-variables, and methods of measuring variables can be explained in the following table:

Table (3): Description and Measuring of the Research Variables

Main Variables		Sub-Variables	Number of Statement	Methods of Measuring Variables
Independent Variable	Woman Leadership	Empathy	4	Desvaux & Devilland, 2007 Rouleau – Carroll, 2014
		Collaboration	4	
		Patience	4	
		Intuitiveness	4	
		Composure	4	
Total WL			20	
Dependent Variable	Psychological Capital	Hope	6	Luthans et al., 2007 Bockorny, 2015
		Optimism	6	
		Resilience	6	
		Self-Efficacy	6	
		Total PsyCap		

9.2. Descriptive Analysis

Before testing the hypotheses and research questions, descriptive statistics were performed to find out means and standard deviations of WL and PsyCap.

Table (4) shows the mean and standard deviations of WL and PsyCap

Variables	The Dimension	Mean	Standard Deviation
WL	Empathy	3.59	1.21
	Collaboration	3.78	1.19
	Patience	3.59	1.21
	Intuitiveness	3.65	1.20
	Composure	4.22	0.621
	Total Measurement	3.77	1.04
PsyCap	Hope	3.47	0.983
	Optimism	3.62	0.971
	Resilience	3.63	0.970
	Self-Efficacy	3.48	0.892
	Total Measurement	3.55	0.940

Table (4) lists the mean and standard deviation among variables. The mean of each variable is more than 3, and this result indicates that the study subjects in general have a higher level of WL and PsyCap. The different facets of WL are examined. Most respondents identified the presence of patience (M=3.59, SD=1.21). This was followed by collaboration (M=3.78, SD=1.19), patience (M=3.59, SD=1.21), intuitiveness (M=3.65, SD=1.20), composure (M=4.22, SD=0.621), and total WL (M=3.77, SD=1.04).

The different facets of PsyCap are examined. Most respondents identified the presence of hope (M=3.47, SD=0.983). This was followed by optimism (M=3.62, SD=0.971), resilience (M=3.63, SD=0.970), self-efficacy (M=3.48, SD=0.892), and total PsyCap (M=3.55, SD=0.940).

9.3. Evaluating Reliability

ACC was used to evaluate the degree of internal consistency among the contents of the scale under testing. Table (5) shows the results of the reliability test for each variable of WL and PsyCap.

Table (5) Reliability of WL and PsyCap

Variables	The Dimension	Number of Statement	ACC
WL	Empathy	4	0.921
	Collaboration	4	0.969
	Patience	4	0.921
	Intuitiveness	4	0.919
	Composure	4	0.661
	Total Measurement	20	0.974
PsyCap	Hope	6	0.833
	Optimism	6	0.822
	Resilience	6	0.815
	Self-Efficacy	6	0.746
	Total Measurement	24	0.955

The 20 items of WL are reliable because the ACC is 0.974. Four items of empathy scales are reliable due to the fact that the ACC is 0.921. The Collaboration, which consists of four items, is reliable since the ACC is 0.969. The four items related to patience are reliable as ACC is 0.921. Furthermore, the intuitiveness, which consists of four items, is reliable due to the fact that the ACC is 0.919. Also, the four items related to composure are reliable as ACC is 0.661.

The 24 items of PsyCap are reliable because the ACC is 0.955. The six items of hope scales are reliable due to the fact that the ACC is 0.833. The optimism, which consists of six items, is reliable since the ACC is 0.822. The six items related to resilience are reliable as ACC is 0.815. Furthermore, the self-efficacy, which consists of six items, is reliable due to the fact that the ACC is 0.746.

9.4. The Means, St. Deviations, and Correlation among Variables

Table (6) Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Matrix for all Variables

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	WL	PsyCap
Woman Leadership	3.77	1.04	1.000	
Psychological Capital	3.55	0.940	0.890**	1.000

Table (6) shows correlation coefficients between the research variables, and results indicate the presence of a significant correlation between variables (WL and PsyCap).

The level of WL of employees is average (Mean=3.77; SD=1.04), while PsyCap is (Mean=3.55; SD= 0.940).

Table (6) reveals the existence of a positive correlation between WL and PsyCap (R=0.890; P < 0.01), which means that the high level of WL leads to higher PsyCap.

9.5. The Correlation between WL and PsyCap

Table (7): Correlation Matrix among WL and PsyCap

Research Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6
Empathy	1					
Collaboration	0.852**	1				
Patience	1.000**	0.852**	1			
Intuitiveness	0.965**	0.843**	0.965**	1		
Composure	0.857**	0.635**	0.857**	0.873**	1	
Psychological Capital	0.880**	0.814**	0.880**	0.894**	0.708**	1

Note: ** Correlation is significant at 0.01 level

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of SPSS, V.23, 2015

Based on the Table (7), the correlation between WL (Empathy) and PsyCap is 0.880. For WL (Collaboration) and PsyCap, the value is 0.814 whereas WL (Patience) and PsyCap show a correlation value of 0.880. Also, the correlation between WL (Intuitiveness) and PsyCap is 0.894 whereas WL (Composure) and PsyCap show a correlation value of 0.708. The overall correlation between WL and PsyCap is 0.890.

9.6. Woman Leadership (Empathy) and PsyCap

The relationship between WL and PsyCap is determined. The first hypothesis to be tested is: *There is no statistically significant relationship between WL (Empathy) and PsyCap at Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt.*

Table (8) MRA Results for WL (Empathy) and PsyCap

The Variables of WL (Empathy)	Beta	R	R ²
1. My boss has communication skills.	0.226**	0.758	0.574
2. My boss provides clear advice when you turn to her.	0.519**	0.878	0.770
3. My boss is always at work, which makes us comfortable	0.056	0.723	0.522
4. My boss share all the employees their feelings	0.160*	0.813	0.660
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Multiple Correlation Coefficients (MCC) ▪ Determination of Coefficient (DF) ▪ The Value of Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ The Value of Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.893 0.797 290.354 4, 295 3.31 0.000	
* P < 0.05 ** P < 0.01			

According to Table (8), the regression-coefficient between WL (Empathy) and PsyCap is R= 0.893 and R²= 0.797. This means that the PsyCap can be explained by the dimensions of WL (Empathy). Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected because WL (Empathy) and PsyCap have a statistical relationship at the significance level of 0.01.

9.7. Woman Leadership (Collaboration) and PsyCap

The relationship between WL and PsyCap is determined. The second hypothesis to be tested is: *There is no statistically significant relationship between WL (Collaboration) and PsyCap at Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt.*

Table (9) The Relationship between WL (Collaboration) and PsyCap

The Variables of WL (Collaboration)	Beta	R	R ²
1. My boss emphasizes on generating ideas to solve performance problems.	0.024	0.765	0.585
2. My boss participates employees in defining the organization's goals.	0.550**	0.814	0.662
3. My boss is interested in involving all employees in organization decisions.	0.223*	0.785	0.616
4. My boss is interested in participating employees in building the organization's vision.	0.046	0.755	0.570
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Multiple Correlation Coefficients (MCC) ▪ Determination of Coefficient (DF) ▪ The Value of Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ The Value of Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.822 0.676 153.533 4, 295 3.31 0.000	
* P < 0.05			

According to Table (9), the regression-coefficient between WL (Collaboration) and PsyCap is R= 0.822 and R²= 0.676. This means that the PsyCap can be explained by the dimensions of WL (Collaboration). Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected because WL (Collaboration) and PsyCap have a statistical relationship at the significance level of 0.01.

9.8. Woman Leadership (Patience) and PsyCap

The relationship between WL and PsyCap is determined. The third hypothesis to be tested is: *There is no statistically significant relationship between WL (Patience) and PsyCap at Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt.*

Table (10) The Relationship between WL (Patience) and PsyCap

The Variables of WL (Patience)	Beta	R	R ²
1. My bosses have patience in dealing with business problems	0.226**	0.758	0.574
2. My boss is involved in more than one task as well as her current job.	0.519**	0.878	0.770
3. My boss reduces negative emotions such as sadness and anger.	0.056	0.723	0.522
4. My boss removes the anxiety that accompanies us when carrying out the tasks.	0.160*	0.813	0.660
▪ Multiple Correlation Coefficients (MCC)	0.893		
▪ Determination of Coefficient (DF)	0.797		
▪ The Value of Calculated F	290.354		
▪ Degree of Freedom	4, 295		
▪ The Value of Indexed F	3.31		
▪ Level of Significance	0.000		
* P < 0.05 ** P < 0.01			

According to Table (10), the regression-coefficient between WL (Patience) and PsyCap is R= 0.893 and R²= 0.797. This means that the PsyCap can be explained by the dimensions of WL (Patience). Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

9.9. Woman Leadership (Intuitiveness) and PsyCap

The relationship between WL and PsyCap is determined. The fourth hypothesis to be tested is:

There is no statistically significant relationship between WL (Patience) and PsyCap at Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt.

Table (11) The Relationship between WL (Intuitiveness) and PsyCap

The Variables of WL (Intuitiveness)	Beta	R	R ²
1. My boss is able to predict the obstacles to work	0.232**	0.758	0.574
2. My boss tests new ideas to ensure their validity.	0.147	0.878	0.770
3. My boss is interested in different points of view when solving problems.	0.527**	0.886	0.784
4. My boss manages the difficulties of working professionally.	0.071	0.694	0.481
▪ Multiple Correlation Coefficients (MCC)	0.906		
▪ Determination of Coefficient (DF)	0.821		
▪ The Value of Calculated F	339.205		
▪ Degree of Freedom	4, 295		
▪ The Value of Indexed F	3.31		
▪ Level of Significance	0.000		
** P < 0.01			

According to Table (11), the regression-coefficient between WL (Intuitiveness) and PsyCap is R= 0.906 and R²= 0.821. This means that the PsyCap can be explained by the dimensions of WL (Intuitiveness). Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected because WL (Intuitiveness) and PsyCap have a statistical relationship at the significance level of 0.01.

9.10. Woman Leadership (Composure) and PsyCap

The relationship between WL and PsyCap is determined. The fifth hypothesis to be tested is:

There is no statistically significant relationship between WL (Composure) and PsyCap at Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt.

According to Table (12), the regression-coefficient between WL (Composure) and PsyCap is R= 0.917 and R²= 0.841. This means that the PsyCap can be explained by the dimensions of WL (Composure). Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected because WL (Composure) and PsyCap have a statistical relationship at the significance level of 0.01.

Table (12) The Relationship between WL (Composure) and PsyCap

The Variables of WL (Composure)	Beta	R	R ²
1. My boss shall bear the results of her decisions.	0.211**	0.649	0.421
2. My boss has the ability to withstand difficult conditions.	0.737**	0.878	0.770
3. My boss overcomes negative emotions.	0.110	0.212	0.044
4. My boss sticks to her positions if they serve the interest of work.	0.168	0.206	0.042
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Multiple Correlation Coefficients (MCC) ▪ Determination of Coefficient (DF) ▪ The Value of Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ The Value of Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.917 0.841 390.926 4, 295 3.31 0.000	
** P < 0.01			

10. Research Results

By reviewing the results of the descriptive analysis of the data on which the study was based and testing the research hypothesis, the study reached a set of results which will be reviewed and discussed as follows:

1. The level of leadership characteristics of women was high, because the leader possesses the characteristics of her advantage effectively and influential on the performance of workers. These characteristics led to their support during situations, and also made them strengthen their position in all circumstances that could work to decline or weaken the organization and its subordinates. In addition, these features hide vulnerabilities that may appear in the absence of one. The study (Rouleau-Carroll, 2014) agrees that the practice of female leadership characteristics is high.
2. The level of empathy is the highest, due to the physiological nature of women that possess and distinguish them from males. This makes them understand the other and can assess the situation and deal with it wisely and logically. They use a clear and explicit method of providing advice. The advice is the result of a continuous presence that urges subordinates to feel comfortable, safe, confident in working, increasing team spirit and sharing among subordinates. According to the study (Vasavada, 2012), the characteristic of empathy strengthens the management of women and improve their relations with subordinates.
3. The level of cooperation is high. This is an indication that this characteristic needs to be further developed and strengthened by increasing the level of participation and interaction between the president and the staff to increase the level of effectiveness. This study is consistent with the (Bruckmuller & Branscombe, 2010) study of the leader's ability to cooperate with subordinates.
4. There is a statistically significant effect of the characteristics of women leaders in the development of PsyCap. This means that the characteristics of women leadership contribute to the development of PsyCap. The characteristics of women in leadership increase the development of the individual's psychology and improve comfort during the presence of work. Thus, it improves the productivity and performance of workers. This finding is consistent with the study (Corner, 2015) that the characteristics of women leaders have an impact on PsyCap.
5. There is a statistically significant impact of the characteristics of women leadership in developing confidence (self-efficacy) due to the nature of women's leadership of workers. This has an impact on the individual by increasing his confidence in himself as his ability to find solutions when facing problems and presenting his proposals in meetings without fear. This finding is consistent with the study (Drasin, 2014) because the characteristics of women leadership support, develop and improve the leadership after the culture of the individual because of its positive impact and developed after the confidence of the individual.
6. There is a statistically significant impact on the characteristics of women's leadership in the development of optimism. As a result of some characteristics in the women such as empathy, patience, and calm, which increases optimism among workers, especially in encouraging them to deal with cases of certainty To reach the desired goals easily.
7. There is a statistically significant impact on the characteristics of women leaders in the development of hope. This is an indication that the characteristics of women leadership contribute to the development of

the individual's ability to expect better at work. This finding is consistent with the study (Corner, 2015) as the characteristics of women leadership influenced the development of hope.

8. There is a statistically significant impact on the characteristics of women leadership in developing resilience. This is an indication of the characteristics of women leaders that will help reduce negative emotions and deal with it. Also, it makes the individual able to deal with the difficult situations and complete work well to reach the goals of the organization and work to develop.
9. The level of characteristics of women leadership was high and this is due to the organization in a positive way.
10. The level of PsyCap was somewhat moderate. This is due to the presence of ineffective practices in the right investment of PsyCap, perhaps the most important of the existence of negative feelings towards the work and poor development of the ability to withstand difficult situations and poor motivation to work diligently.

11. Recommendations

In the light of the previous results, the researcher concluded with a set of recommendations as follows:

1. Increase and strengthen the practices of women's leadership characteristics. This is due to the positive impact on subordinates, through increased support to senior management, documenting successful experiences, and capacity development through specialized training programs.
2. The need to pay attention to the PsyCap significantly. This is due to its importance and its impact on the psychology and the work of the individual in the organization and because of the benefits and competitive advantage of the organization.
3. Allow women in the fields of recruitment and involve them more in work to nurture their strength of expertise.
4. The need not to limit women because they are women only and leave this negative culture because women have high leadership skills that excelled by and elevated the field of work.
5. The need to continue to look for the characteristics of women's leadership, which is due to the availability, but did not write much, and urge to invest in PsyCap. This will be through further studies where there is a clear lack of those studies on the one hand and the urgent need for them on the other.
6. The necessity and importance of researching the characteristics of women leadership in different sectors.

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